

Intercultural Education from the students' perspective in a Home Internationalization Program from PUCPR/

A Educação Intercultural sob a perspectiva dos estudantes em um Programa de Internacionalização em Casa da PUCPR

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Received in: 06 dec. 2024. **Approved** in: 08 dec. 2024.

How to mention this article:

HACK, Katleen da Silva; FERNANDES, Karina Aires Reinlein. Intercultural Education from the students' perspective in a Home Internationalization Program from PUCPR. *Revista Letras Raras*. Campina Grande, v. 13, n. 5, e5409, dec. 2024. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14563681>

ABSTRACT

The ongoing search for internationalization processes in Higher Education has led Brazilian universities to incorporate actions that contribute to the student's integration into this context. Considering the student as an agent who plays an important role in the planning, implementing, and evaluating language policies within universities, this study aimed to investigate the profile and perspectives of the students enrolled in the Global Classes courses, an initiative implemented as Internationalization at Home at PUCPR, based on a questionnaire answered by 97 higher education students. The

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research was based on the objectives set up by the institution and was compared with the students' perceptions based on intercultural competencies and language policies. The focus of the analysis aimed to understand the effectiveness of the planning provided to students as positive and their understanding of the courses taught in a second language as a contributing factor to their education. The results showed that the subjects incorporate cultural themes that are relevant both in the Brazilian context and internationally and are open to the entire university. As a result, there were reports of positive experiences and a lack of awareness regarding the methodologies applied in the classroom, as well as no indication of learning about the context of use and linguistic variation. Thus, it is understood that this program can be incorporated implicitly, given the reports of intercultural discussions, but even so, language policies can be explored through institutional practices that engage students from different backgrounds.

KEYWORDS: Internationalization at Home; Interculturality; Linguistic Policies; Higher Education Students.

RESUMO

A constante busca pelos processos de internacionalização no Ensino Superior fez com que as universidades brasileiras incorporassem ações que contribuíssem para a inserção dos estudantes nesse contexto. Pensando no estudante como o agente que desempenha um importante papel dentro do processo de planejamento, implementação e avaliação das políticas linguísticas dentro das universidades é que esse trabalho investigou o perfil e perspectiva dos alunos inseridos nas disciplinas Global Classes, uma ação realizada como Internacionalização em Casa da PUCPR, a partir de um questionário respondido por 97 estudantes da educação superior. Ao realizar essa pesquisa, foram comparados os objetivos previstos pela instituição em relação à visão dos estudantes, baseando-se nas atribuições interculturais e de políticas linguísticas. O foco da análise previu compreender a efetivação do planejamento feito aos estudantes como positiva e a compreensão dos alunos sobre as disciplinas lecionadas em um segundo idioma como fator contribuinte na formação. Como resultados, observou-se que as disciplinas incorporam temáticas culturais, inseridas tanto no contexto brasileiro como a nível internacional, sendo abertas para os estudantes de toda a universidade. Com isso, houve relato de experiências positivas e de desconhecimento sobre as metodologias postas em sala, além da não indicação da aprendizagem sobre contexto de uso e variação linguística em sala. Desse modo, entende-se que essas atividades podem ser incorporadas de modo implícito, vistos os relatos que afirmam discussões de forma intercultural, porém, ainda assim, as políticas linguísticas podem ser exploradas por meio de práticas institucionais de engajamento com alunos de diferentes perfis.

PALAVRAS-CHAVE: Internacionalização em Casa; Interculturalidade; Políticas Linguísticas; Estudantes do Ensino Superior.

1 Introduction

Based on the globalized communication in which today's population is established, internationalization and multilingualism are necessary for integrating with social demands. Accompanying this outpouring, universities are looking for ways to insert themselves into this context by presenting alternatives that incorporate teaching into contact with a Second Language (L2). In this regard, considering that learning is an agent of multiversity, it is necessary that objectives set by internationalization programs can reach different social, cultural, and linguistic fields.

According to Lunardi *et al.* (2019, p.133), language policy is the foundation for internationalization in higher education since “Internationalization emphasizes the relationship between nations, peoples, cultures, institutions, and systems. It concerns the free circulation of science and technologies between countries or, in other words, the process of globalization of scientific knowledge.” Thus, internationalization activities should be open to all individuals, as language enables professional training and citizen education about other cultures.

In this way, the Pontifical Catholic University of Paraná (PUCPR) seeks to insert a context of Internationalization at Home (IaH) that involves students, professors, and monitors in developing language proficiency and confidence in bilingual communication. To set up this action, the idea proposed by the Director of International Relations (DI) aims to enable integration with foreign languages through specific subjects, integrated with a second language (PUCPR, 2018), which emerged as English Semester and now are called Global Classes.

Thus, this research investigates how the program is implemented, comparing the official university documents with the student’s perspective to trace the profile included in the project and the effectiveness of the subjects in the student’s intercultural training. This is followed by an analysis of the responses of 97 participating students, looking at possible limitations and gaps in student training according to the view of each respondent. This analysis is made with the justification that PUCPR developed this project to improve the learning process and promote multicultural experiences with respect for diversity and global perspectives, and therefore, it is relevant to understand whether this action is favorable.

That being so, to examine the scenario obtained, the following theoretical references were selected: Baranzeli (2019), Lunardi *et al.* (2019), and Nunes (2019), who analyze learning in teaching internationalization at home, presenting language policy, interculturality, and cognitive and socio-emotional competences as possibilities and strategies for teaching. Consequently, this research assumes the qualitative state that has as its “purpose to study the life experience of people and complex social environments, according to the perspective of the social actors themselves” (Gil, 2019, p. 7), taking the questionnaire in parallel with the literature and the official documents of the PUCPR program.

2 The students and the Internationalization at Home: the Interculturality in the learning process

Among the internationalization programs, Internationalization at Home (IaH) is a “subset of the Internationalization of the Curriculum, a process distinct from mobility, which should focus on all students” (Baranzeli, 2019, p. 188). Thus, this model brings together various international and intercultural activities made available by the university, such as research, extension, lectures, etc., to enrich the experience of many interested students.

In 2022, PUCPR offered “169 courses [...] in seven different languages, attracting more than 10,000 registrations by more than 3,800 students” (PUCPR, 2023, p. 2), as well as international events, short-term programs, and exchange incentives. Based on this, the hub covered by this model is broad and makes it possible to include different profiles in its action plan. In this way, the university takes as its principles both the provision of tools for the institution’s local and international audiences, which demand different functions. According to PUCPR’s objectives (2018, p. 2), the following are launched for local undergraduate students:

- a. To provide a complete, diverse deduction aimed at broadening opportunities to enter the international arena, utilizing a differentiated academic background, with an impact on the curriculum and the enhancement of their professional careers.
- b. Promote opportunities to analyze knowledge from different perspectives.
- c. Providing contact with international students in the classroom environment and context, favoring the insertion mentioned in point a, without the need for international mobility.
- d. Provide the opportunity to develop a command of technical language in a foreign language and establish a global network of contacts.

As a result, it can be understood that both through the link between students and international opportunities and through the specific learning of the foreign language subject, it is possible to establish integrative dimensions in L2 that activate intercultural factors through communication and learning. Thus, it is understood that different elements may or may not be incorporated by institutions according to the proposal defined by each context in which the project is carried out, the ones seen above chosen by PUCPR. Baranzeli (2019, p. 196) points out that there are multiple instruments for carrying out IaH, among which we can highlight those shown below:

Picture 1. IaH Practical tools Ferramentas

Source: Elaborated by Baranzeli (2019) based on Beelen (2017)., translated by the authors (2024)

According to the objectives defined by PUCPR's Internationalization plan (2018), some of these methods are related to those established for students, such as comparing cases and literature produced in different contexts and welcoming foreign students. With this, it is possible to understand that the PUCPR material seeks to achieve the linguistic and cultural diversity through which the foreign language permeates as it aims for approaches that provide an intercultural and international perspective, contributing to the strengthening and intertwining of these concepts in the field of Higher Education" (Albizu Ontaneda, 2014 *apud* Baranzeli, 2019).

From this perspective, it is understood that the learning process requires, in the different challenges that encompass international connections, the ability of students to develop intercultural and linguistic skills, which can be limited depending on the methodology, regulations, or classroom interaction that do not provide adequate support for the development of these skills. In this connection, Nunes (2019, p. 211) indicates that "it is up to education institutions to contribute to the integral development of students, from the perspective of the development of multiple dimensions, namely intellectual, emotional, social, physical and cultural," which emphasizes the configuration in the classroom, the selection of teaching material and other internationalization activities as shaping the development of each student profile, since they permeate different dimensions.

According to the Global Classes Manual (PUCPR, 2018), subjects taught in another language have been classified as follows: level 1 Global Classes (GCL1) have teaching and bibliographic material available in the foreign language and Portuguese, and Portuguese are used in the classroom,

with the use of the foreign language being acceptable. At level 2 (GCL2), teaching and bibliographic material are available in both languages, and the classroom uses the foreign language, with the use of Portuguese being acceptable. Level 3 (GCL3) provides materials and classroom discussions in the foreign language. Finally, level 4 (GCL4) takes into account the existing partnership between PUCPR and other universities through COIL (*Collaborative Online International Learning*), so subjects are taught in a hybrid way by local and global professors.

There are also three types of courses on offer: distance learning, face-to-face, and semi-presential. In addition, monitors are available through the university's Monitoring Program, and complementary foreign language activities are offered through PUC Acolhe and PUC Idiomas. Through these actions by the institution, the integration between language and content is not just in the classroom but encompasses other areas of the institution and integrates different levels of knowledge and availability, which are understood to be necessary and used by students in a way that is beneficial to learning.

In this way, one should consider not only one way of using the language in the classroom but also the different uses in real contexts, taking into account the groups of speakers present in the spheres in which the language circulates. This shows the importance of recognizing and addressing the concept of lingua franca and language policy, as Sousa e Soares (2014, p. 104) point out:

Practices are the language choices that members of a given speech Community make in their daily lives, such as choosing a specific variety to fulfill a certain communicative function, choosing a linguistic variant to suit the interlocutor, choosing which variety to use to show or hide an identity, among others.

As a model of laH, understanding the plurality of actions and competencies of international teaching can help in the acquisition and integration with the real environment in which the L2 is located because, in addition to the exchange with exchange students, cultural diversity, global perspectives, the concept of lingua franca, international collaboration and the integration of experiences are propagated. Moreira (2001, p. 31) suggests that this is a necessary initiative, since:

The "others," those who are different, are often close to us and even inside us, but we are not used to seeing them, hearing them, recognizing them, valuing them, and

interacting with them. In the society we live in, there is a dynamic building up of situations of social and cultural segregation that confine different socio-cultural groups in different spaces, where only those considered equal have access. At the same time, there is a multiplication of bars, walls, and distances, not only physical but also emotional and symbolic, between people and groups whose cultural identities are differentiated by issues of social, ethnic, gender, and religious belonging, etc.

In this way, intercultural education is an emerging reaction to the concept of internationalization, as it promotes the union of different groups to open knowledge and citizen development. As a result, in addition to the differences between local and exchange students, it is also important for this process to bring together different profiles within the local multiculturalism present at the university, as well as disciplines that encourage this discussion.

3 Students' Perspectives on Global Classes

Based on the questionnaire applied to students taking part in the university's Global Classes disciplines, the answers about the students' expectations and perceptions in the reaching context were analyzed. From this, we seek to understand the PUCPR university's plan concerning the application to local students, with a view to perceiving education as an intercultural and linguistic factor.

3.1 Methodology and L2 Teaching

Since it is important to create subjects that promote intercultural initiatives beyond direct contact with outsiders, the PUCPR documents (2018, p.1) show that the construction of Global Classes subjects includes multicultural factors in the learning process:

- a. Increasing PUCPR's internationalization process by broadening the horizons of the student body and the teaching staff, turning their gaze to the globalized world;
- b. Strengthen the use of foreign languages across the various schools and administrative units of the institution;
- c. Democratize internationalization through a broad and biased action of internationalization at home, the aim of which is to encourage the inclusion of

the academic community of students, professors, professor-tutors, and collaborators in the global environment, regardless of international mobility.

As seen above, the subjects are geared towards globalized knowledge from a transversal perspective, in which not only students but also professors, monitors, and collaborators are involved in promoting a bilingual process. From the students' responses, it is clear that this openness allows professors and students to have subjects available in distinct areas. As it is a university-wide initiative, the diversity between courses and schools helps to broaden information and language knowledge in various spaces, both inside and outside academic content. In this respect, some of the responses below are worth mentioning.

Table 1 – Global Classes taken by PUCPR students

Student 1	Discursive Practices of English Language I, II, III and IV. Oral and Written Practices in English Language, Translation Studies, Literature of English-Speaking Countries I and II. Oral Practice in English Language, <i>Taxonomy - Reading and Analyzing Scientific Terminology</i>
Student 2	<i>Accounting Statements, Entrepreneurial Management, Strategic Human Resources Management, Principles of Marketing, Business English, Business Economics E Organizational Design</i>
Student 3	Relação Parasita-hospedeiros, Inglês Acadêmico, Raciocínio Integrador, Sistemas Nefro-urogenital, Cardiorrespiratório, Endócrino, Metabólico E Nutricional, Hematológico, Habilidades Profissionais, Célula E Base Molecular Da Vida Etc.
Student 4	<i>Human Rights: International Protection System</i>
Student 5	<i>Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning</i>
Student 6	<i>Futuro De Las Ciudades De La Latina America</i>
Student 7	Bebidas e Alimentos fermentados e de farinha de plantas não convencionais (PANCS)

Source: elaborated by these research authors.

Looking at the subjects highlighted by the students, it is remarkable how they incorporate cultural themes since each area has its themes that are inserted in the Brazilian context, but also under international studies. However, not only the exposure of these themes should be a parameter of interculturality, but also the development of intercultural competencies (IC). Regarding this definition, Clemente (2019, p. 54) specifies that intercultural competence is a complex construct that involves more than one component, and internationalization strategies need to address the development of IC components in various ways". Among those mentioned by the author, we can highlight "coursework, study abroad, interaction on campus (with students from different cultural backgrounds, etc.) [...]

various assessment methods to measure intercultural competence”. Based on this statement, Global Classes subjects are available in the following forms: compulsory, in courses with a second language, and elective/optional, all of which are free for the entire institution when part of the curriculum. In this way, it is open to any interested student to participate in subjects that are not common to their course and for exchange students to enroll in those that interest them the most.

Based on this, it can be observed from the author’s comments that interaction between students and global perspectives align with the concepts of intercultural competence, which relate to interaction on campus and involvement in undergraduate and postgraduate courses. This contributes to a more positive engagement with learning, addressing distinct global and local themes and contexts. Based on this perception, it is possible to consider the students’ responses about the understanding of the disciplines being integrated with second language acquisition because, from these perspectives, it can be noticed whether the action plan produces this optimistic effect on L2 learning.

Picture 2 – Do you believe that the course content is integrated with the learning of a second language?

9. Do you believe that the course content is integrated with the learning of a second language?

96 answers

Source: Global Classes Survey – *Um Estudo sobre a Perspectiva e Perfil dos Envolvidos no Programa de Internacionalização da PUCPR* (2024).

According to Picture 2, the majority of students perceive the Global Classes disciplines as being in line with L2 learning, but there are still responses of ignorance about this relationship, with 11.5% no and 14.6% yes. Graph 2 below shows that the methodology used in the classroom can

influence this perception, as 32.5% of the students are not aware of, or have not been able to evaluate, the methodology used by the professor and, as a result, may not feel that the proposals adopted in teaching are leading to effective learning of the language and the skills and elements that make up communication in L2:

Picture 3 – Do you know what methodological strategies your professor uses in class??

10. Do you know what methodological strategies your teacher uses in class?

96 answers

Source: Global Classes Survey – *Um Estudo sobre a Perspectiva e Perfil dos Envolvidos no Programa de Internacionalização da PUCPR (2024)*.

Based on the methodology used, it is possible to establish intercultural factors, in addition to the language, through activities that promote interaction, discussion, and a critical look at the material and content worked on in class. For this reason, unfamiliarity can be an element to be explored by the professor and the institution, clarifying choices made about the way of teaching in the classroom and establishing a safe environment in which the student recognizes and expresses expectations and motivations about the subject and learning. In this respect, some of the students' answers point to different methodologies they understand and how these proposals have influenced their studies, based on the question: "Do you believe that the teaching strategies used contribute to your learning?":

- Yes, because the professor included the students in her class every moment, allowing them to read the content to the whole class, which helped with reading and listening, solving the exercises in class, and presenting their solutions, which contributed to the understanding and absorption of the content; (Student 8)

- I think so. Because they challenge me to go further in the foreign language, I know that if I had been exposed to the English language in a face-to-face or online language course, I wouldn't have challenged myself so much to write in English, to read, to present work, to try to use all the language knowledge I have, even with pronunciation mistakes or verb tenses sometimes. (Student 9)
- They collaborate, but they are not the goal, they happen as a consequence. It requires proactivity on the part of the student. (Student 10)
- Not really. I thought we would use more English in class, but apparently, the other students don't feel comfortable with it. (Student 11)

Based on the students' comments, it is possible to identify the distinct methods used in the classroom. Some examples are active methodologies that place the student at the center of the process; improvement focused on writing and solving exercises, and the influence that colleagues and professional motivation have on the teaching environment. Regarding this freedom of choice, which means that each subject can be managed differently, PUCPR (2018) mentions that the professor is free to choose how to work with their subject, which means that each subject is linked to the model that best fits the activities style of the course. In this way, it is understood that the possibility of adaption is beneficial for the construction of the lesson but can be disadvantageous for students who come from outside the area or who are looking for a different proposal to the one proposed by the professor. This strengthens the possibility of defining and presenting methodological strategies to the students as a way of getting to know and using the abilities of diversity and, consequently, intercultural relations.

It is necessary to consider the background and perspectives of these professors. A professor's professional identity is the foundation of any educational program, as they are the ones who will have direct contact with the students, and it is their training and education that distinguishes them.

According to Branco (2019, p. 16), this is a "[...] continuous process of self-education aimed at deepening knowledge to improve oneself, one's students, and one's environment. However, Marcelino e Verniano (2022, p. 131) points out that, in general, research on the subject "[...] focuses on issues of approaches, methodologies and teaching philosophies, leaving the professor's linguistic training to work in this context in the background". In addition, Graves (2000 *apud* Fernandes, 2021) argues that professor's decisions are often influenced by the context in which they live and work, as well as previous experiences and personal beliefs.

In this context, Baranzeli (2019, p. 191) indicates that “professors must be open and listen to what is new and different, engage with the proposal and be willing to put it into practice,” understanding that there are fundamental characteristics for those working in internationalization model classes. For example, some of the characteristics cited by the author are: “Knowing the characteristics of the students; Updating the topics covered in class; Improving the dynamics proposed in groups; Interest in knowledge and multi/interdisciplinary work; Verifying the material used (own construction/bibliography).” With this in mind, it is clear that methodology in the context of internationalization should be a space that welcomes unlike teaching techniques since professors are also the target of this development process. However, some aspects can be included in all methods of working with a second language, such as adapting the teaching environment to the profile of the internationalization class and the materials used, as this helps to identify linguistic and cultural competencies directly in the learning process.

It is also important to note that there is currently a limited supply of courses and training for professors in bilingual contexts (Salgado *et al.*, 2009), which can be an obstacle to the development of in-service training in this area. One of the distinguishing features of PUCPR is the inclusion of these professors in training courses such as the *Faculty Development Course: Teaching in a Second Language*, which was offered in 2019 to deans and internationalization agents of the university to discuss linguistic issues, providing pedagogical tools and increasing the motivation of those involved to offer subjects taught in other languages¹. In 2024, the course was offered to the Toledo campus² to internationalization agents, course coordinators, and professors who were interested in learning more about the international context and promoting the offer of courses in other languages, Global Classes. The application of the course has already led to greater motivation in the offers and perspectives of the professors, but we recognize the need to train other groups of professors in the institution.

3.1 Expectations and Student Learning in Global Classes

¹ <https://www.pucpr.br/international/news/english-as-a-medium-of-instruction-emi-classes-have-just-started/>

² <https://www.pucpr.br/noticias/eeh-realiza-curso-de-formacao-de-professores-para-oferta-de-global-classes/>

By understanding that there is a variety of choices and methodologies presented in L2 and that this approach can mobilize different skills, whether they are understood by the students or not, we can try to understand what the student's expectations are and whether they are in line with the plan of the Global Classes internationalization program. With this in mind, the table below can be analyzed:

Table 2 – What were your expectations When selecting the subject(s)?

Student 1	Having the experience of studying in another language, improving my language skills.
Student 2	An opportunity to develop myself better in the English language, as well as learning a new subject in another language.
Student 3	That it would add to my career.
Student 4	Mainly to increase my vocabulary in the subject content.
Student 5	Learning about the themes and axes proposed in the subject, since it is a current theme, thus enabling an understanding of the formation of urgent and emerging cities in Latin America.
Student 6	I thought it was going to be a course with foreign students and entirely in English.
Student 7	An addition to my bilingual education.
Student 8	Sharing knowledge / practicing conversation.
Student 9	Be 100% in contact with the English language during classes and learn about the different ways of behaving in different cultures.
Student 10	A large group of Exchange students from various countries interacting with each other, getting to know each other's cultures and learning new things, in a different way from what we usually learn.

Source: elaborated by these research authors.

As can be visible in the table, most expectations are related to language improvement and communication, but also to contact with other cultures, which shows the recognition of global skills as a necessary factor on both a personal and professional level. According to the PUCPR's internationalization plan (2023, p. 1), "In a scenario of intense and unforeseen transformations such as the current one, a Higher Education Institution (HEI) fails when it does not seek to train professionals and citizens who are part of the global community and capable of acting in distinct contexts and cultures." In this way, the subjects reflect a search for current themes that contribute to ethical practices in the real context.

With this perception, it is understood that the students are getting close to the proposals made in class and to the understanding of learning through the L2, which is not limited to the exchange or

isolated use of the language but is contextualized with the culture and linguistic plurality of each country and territory. On this basis, it can be said that teaching in an intercultural context at PUCPR makes progress in the student's perception of the different components that are present in the acquisition of a second language, incorporating language policies that, according to Sousa and Soares (2014, p. 105 *apud* Spolsky 2004, 2009, 2012):

a) they happen at a different level of the language, from a dimension related to the micro level to the macro level (e.g., “Pronounce this word correctly” or “Don’t use dialect. Use Italian”); b) they operate in linguistic communities of different sizes (e.g., family, school, church, neighborhood, city). C) they may be implicit but can be analyzed in the practices and beliefs of the speakers; d) they involve a range of linguistic as well as non-linguistic factors (e.g., political, demographic, religious, cultural, psychological, economic...).

Based on this conception, we can observe the elements described in the students’ answers, trying to see if they are being used throughout the courses and understood by students in training. Some of the answers can be seen below:

Table 3 – Do you think the Global Classes are meeting your initial expectations?

Student 1	Yes, I’m learning new things in my second language and I’m putting it into practice, without having to pay a lot of money (to study abroad)
Student 2	Partially, sometimes I get so focused on using English that I end up not delving into the content
Student 3	No, I expected to feel like an expert in the language after 4 years of Global Classes, but I still feel at an intermediate level. There is a proficiency barrier, so much so that some classmates can’t even write well or speak in English in their final year
Student 4	Yes, I took it last semester, and everything went very smoothly, just as I wrote above, I increased my repertoire, improved my oratory and acquired knowledge related to the subject of the Global Classes
Student 5	Yes, since I’m receiving teaching material in another language
Student 6	They are not. For now, only in Portuguese
Student 7	Mostly yes. I had hoped that the lower-level subjects (1 and 2) would go mor in-depth into language teaching
Student 8	For me, they meet expectations, yes, because I always wanted to have this space to improve and practice my English. I’m also very happy to be able to help my classmates who don’t speak the languages as naturally as I do.
Student 9	I certainly didn’t have high expectations, I was afraid that I wouldn’t be able to keep up with the language, but the professors have helped me a lot.
Student 10	Yes, because, in general, there is a lot of use of the language and, although there are few of them, I met some students from different countries and cultures, which made for an interesting cultural exchange.

Student 11	Yes, I've finished the subject, but the whole course was satisfactory. The only problem is that we're much more "untamable" than we think. The students from Brazil take a long time to get along with the exchange students, and the international students also take a long time to get along with us. When there are many from the same country, they only relate to each other, and we end up forming isolated groups. The exchange students who come in groups from their own countries also usually combine to do the same subjects, so they only relate to each other because they already know each other – it's more comfortable for them to be isolated with those they already know, because they're in a different culture, with new people.
Student 12	They bring different perspectives on urbanization as well as getting to know other professionals in the field in other parts of the world.
Student 13	We study how to deal with cultural differences and how best to teach English in multicultural environments.
Student 14	Internationalization is the focus of many people's interests today, including my own, and I thought it was great to have the opportunity to see a subject that I wouldn't see just by taking the subjects on the syllabus, and while practicing another language. The debates on this subject really opened my mind to a lot of issues that I had never thought about, related to various areas of law. I acquired knowledge that is essential to be able to reflect on and discuss issues such as the excess of appeals used in civil proceedings and the source of this problem, and even what measures in the area of criminal law are effective in reducing the number of crimes.

Source: elaborated by these research authors.

From the information above, students have unlike experiences depending on the level of language used in the classroom and their exposure to the English language, either through exchange students or the materials used in the classroom. The reports suggest that some aspects of teaching and learning could be further developed. Based on the language policies seen above, the use of different levels of the language is not emphasized by the students. On the other hand, about the language communities, there are mentions of distinct countries, cultures, and the perception of behaviors specific to each group, which in general contributes, even if implicitly, to a broadening of global knowledge about individuals and the subject being worked on in the classroom.

From the concept of inclusion of non-linguistic factors, we can see the incorporation of topics that broaden the student's knowledge, such as cultural differences, language teaching, urbanization, and areas within the law. These reports show that the program works to integrate concepts and develops with the integration of all the differences present in the student's context. In this way, some of the responses present limitations in terms of language, in the idea that the lower levels don't have direct contact with de L2, or in the development of activities that bring the groups of students closer together and promote open discussions about the use of language in multicultural environments.

Therefore, it is understood that there are proposals for integration between students aimed at understanding and dissolving gaps, as PUCPR (2023) shows with the promotion of internationalization events and “Internationalization Clubs” by the university’s schools. Through the student’s responses, only one comment showed knowledge of all the internationalization initiatives: “exchange, double degree, alumni, buddy program, summer institute,” which refers to the importance of this engagement with the program’s proposals. From this research, it is understood that there is the promotion of initiatives that seek to implement the university’s resources and integrate students into the internationalization program.

Final considerations

Based on the results of the survey, it is considered that PUCPR’s Internationalization at Home program provides multiple access for students to seek opportunities for a bilingual experience and to be inserted in a global theme. In this way, the Global Classes present themselves as a way to produce, within the different schools and disciplines of each course, an experience that broadens knowledge at the national level and promotes discussion and communication about the challenges, research, and diversity present in unique cultures and communities.

In this respect, the students are involved in subjects that are part of the context planned by the university, with methodological freedom that allows improvements and investigations in the search for better teaching and learning conditions in the classroom. To this extent, it has been analyzed that there are opportunities to extend the concepts adopted in these methodologies, mainly through students’ academic growth but also through faculty development, which contributes to the improvement of multiple skills in both groups.

Therefore, when observing that many students report not knowing or understanding the methodologies and approaches seen in the classroom as related to L2 teaching, it is still possible to explore the integration and diffusion of the means available at the university to allow more groups to participate and broaden their education through linguistic, cultural and social knowledge.

By broadening the profiles included in the program, it is possible to generate greater debate and a wealth of learning within the academic environment. From the responses, in some cases, there are difficulties in the interaction between the local and international Community, which can be promoted based on methodologies that provide a safe and welcoming environment – highlighting the opportunity for class discussions that make room for world knowledge about the singular context of each student. This makes it possible to mediate and open interaction between students.

Furthermore, in addition to the implicit integration of language policies present in real second-language communication scenarios, it is possible to expand the student’s mastery of the program and the intercultural and global competencies that permeate IaH, which promotes autonomy and self-regulation over expectations and ways to improve the way they learn in class. Given this, the university offers suggestions for integration and the promotion of events that can be a way to dispel doubts and build trust and motivation.

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Acknowledgement:
Financing: Not applicable.
Conflicts of interest: The authors certify that they have no commercial or associative interest that represents a conflict of interest in relation to the manuscript.
Ethical Approval: The research was submitted to and approved by the Ethics Committee: PUCPR . Process. 69833523.5.0000.0020, Approval.: 6.536.058.
Contributor Roles:
HACK, Katleen da Silva. Conceptualization, Data curation, Formal Analysis, Funding acquisition, Investigation, Methodology, Project administration, Resources, Software, Supervision, Validation, Visualization, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing.
FERNANDES, Karina Aires Reinlein. Conceptualization, Data curation, Formal Analysis, Funding acquisition, Investigation, Methodology, Project administration, Resources, Software, Supervision, Validation, Visualization, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing.

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